

FRACTAL APPROACHES IN FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITES

Vadim.V.Silberschmidt

Institute for Structure Mechanics DLR, D-3300 Braunschweig, Germany

Permanent address: *Mining Institute, Ural Dept. of the Russian Academy of Sciences,
78A K.Marx Street, 614007, Perm, Russia*

ABSTRACT

The spatiotemporal evolution of fracture process in stochastic composites is studied on the base of a combination of continuum approach to description of medium with microdefects and fractal theory for accounting the stochastic character of the fracture. The later causes the difference of local stiffness and spatial scatter of damage accumulation kinetics. The analysis of brittle fracture must include a possibility of strong fragmentation (formation of multiple intersecting fracture surfaces) and account for the crack-damage interaction. The application of the fractal approach is studied for the 2D problems. All the non-uniformity of the mechanical properties and stochastic character of the fracture kinetics is taken into account for by setting a distribution of these parameters along the elementary representative volumes (unit cells) in a random way. The influence of the stochastic distribution parameters on the scaling (both spatial and temporal) properties of the fracture evolution is examined.

Keywords: stochastic composites, brittle fracture, crack-microcracks interaction, fractal theory

1. INTRODUCTION

The peculiarities of the brittle fracture of stochastic materials (stochastic composites and brittle rocks being examples) are linked with the marked heterogeneity of such materials which influences the non-uniform development of failure. The real picture of the fracture is also complicated by the existence of different structural (scale) levels which effect fracture development in different ways. Thus, the adequate description of the spatiotemporal fracture development in stochastic materials should account for not only the real geometry and acting

macroscopic loadings but also for the microscopic processes which develop in strongly heterogeneous media. The modelled heterogeneity, in its turn, should reflect the results of the experimental study, both mechanical and structural. The traditional approaches for fracture analysis of the stochastic materials could be roughly divided into two large groups. The first group exploits the continuum approaches with the different averaging procedures (thus obtaining the effective properties of materials), the second elaborates microscopic (structural or semi-structural) fracture models.

The recent progress in this problem is linked with the introduction of relatively modern physical ideas, based on the percolation theory [1] and the theory of fractals [2-8]. The fractal approach in addition to the traditional concentration fracture criterion of the percolation models of failure provides also with the topological parameters of fractured surface and thus allows the spatiotemporal development to be more adequately characterized. The interest to the fractal approaches was stimulated both by the marked progress in the application of fractals in various fields [9-12] and by the elaboration of the experimental procedures for the direct estimation of the fractal dimension of fracture surface [13-15]. The first fractal approaches were based on traditional structural models and exploited relatively simple representation for material's unit cells behaviour: mainly string or rod elements [16,17]. Recent stage of investigation is linked with the use of more complicated approaches: multifractals, self-organized criticality, etc. The adequate description also should account for the real fracture mechanisms in terms of additional structure parameters, The paper is devoted to the combination of the fractal theory with the continuum damage mechanics for the elaboration of the brittle fracture model for stochastic materials.

2. DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN STOCHASTIC MATERIAL: FRACTAL MODEL

Damage evolution (generation, growth and coalescence of microdefects) is one of the main mechanisms of brittle fracture. In common case the account for the damage accumulation is possible on the basis of evolution law (kinetic equation) for damage parameter [18-20] and account for the stress redistribution linked with the damage (traditionally performed in terms of effective stress). The account for the structural stochasticity we shall carry out on the basis of the fractal approach, using the Cayley tree as an analog of the discretization scheme of the region of space under study [21-23]. The transition from the the level $n = 0$ of the fractal tree to the lower (n-th) one corresponds to the division of the region under study into L^n parts, L being a coordination number. Each branch of the n-th level thus corresponds to the structural element of the region making up $1/L^n$ part of the entire volume.

Let us consider this region to be the cross-section of the rectangular beam loaded with a constant force S^* on its ends far from the cross-section under study. The direction of the force is perpendicular to the region which is discretized up to the the level $n = N^*$ until the unit cell dimensions correspond to the requirement of the elementary volume. All the non-uniformity of the mechanical properties and stochastic character of the damage accumulation will be taken into account on the N^* -th level by setting the distribution of these parameters along the elementary volumes in a random way. The character of such a distribution is defined by experimental data and must reflect in general both non-uniformity of the material's strength properties and difference in the rates of development of the ensemble of defects at various points of the material. For the modelled situation we consider that all the material's stochasticity is linked with the stiffness non-uniformity.

For the case under study (uniaxial loading) the system of the constitutive equations can be reduced to the load distribution law for structural elements according to their stiffness and to the kinetic quasi-linear equation of damage accumulation

$$S_i^n = S^* G_i^n / G, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{p}_i^{N^*} = A S_i^{N^*} + B p_i^{N^*}. \quad (2)$$

Here S_i^n, G_i^n are load and stiffness, respectively of the i -th element of the n -th level,

$S^* = \sum_{i=1}^{L^n} S_i^n, G = \sum_{i=1}^{L^n} G_i^n$ ($n = \overline{1, N^*}$) are the total load and stiffness and $G_i^{N^*}$ is a random magnitude set by the random number generator; $p_i^{N^*}$ - the value of damage parameter of the i -th element of the N^* -th level; A, B are the constants which in general form can also be random magnitudes. The model distribution of $G_i^{N^*}$ can be defined by the formula

$$G_i^{N^*} = G_q \left\{ 1 + \left(\sin \frac{\pi i}{L^{N^*}} \right)^q \right\} \quad (i \text{ is a random integer}) \quad (3)$$

so that the ratio of maximum stiffness to minimum one equals 2. Parameter q is the extent of material's uniformity; it is linked with the effective coefficient of distribution's half-width by the relation:

$$K_{0.5} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\pi} \arcsin \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \right). \quad (4)$$

Introduction of Equation (3) means the transition from the self-similar tree to a stochastic one.

The system of state equations (1),(2) should be accompanied by the local fracture criterion for the unit cell. It could be formulated in the form analogous to the concentration criterion:

$$p_i^{N^*} = p_{cr} \quad , \quad (5)$$

where p_{cr} in common case could be also a randomly distributed parameter. The experimental study shows that the pre-fracture volume concentration of defects is equal 0.1 per cent, thus in our calculations $p_{cr} = 0.001$. The development of the fracture process in the region under study will correspond to the motion up the fractal tree; that is the condition of the transition process to the K -th level can be the fracture of all branches (structural elements) of the $(K+1)$ -th level coming from the common node of the K -th level.

Fracture of a structural element (breakage of a corresponding branch) leads to a load redistribution on the other elements within the limits of a joint node of the fractal tree. In this way the macrodefect disturbs a stress state in the region having the radius correlated with the size of the defect itself. Such an overload leads to an activation of the fracture processes in the adjoining elements. As a result a fractal cluster is formed from the failed elements leading to the a fragmentation or a complete fracture (breaking off) of the cross-section.

The fractal dimension of the cluster was obtained for various values of the relative half-width of the distribution (numerical simulations were carried out for the net of $M = L^6 = 4096$ elements)

$$\begin{aligned} D_{HB} &= 1.55 \pm 0.04 & \text{for } K_{0.5} &= 0.1683 \quad , \\ D_{HB} &= 1.64 \pm 0.05 & \text{for } K_{0.5} &= 0.25 \quad , \\ D_{HB} &= 1.76 \pm 0.05 & \text{for } K_{0.5} &= 0.4997 \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In order to fulfill the condition of the equality of the total stiffness of the cross section for all cases for all cases of stochastic distribution the relation connecting G_q with the main case $q=2$ (for $M \gg 1$):

$$G_q = \frac{3}{2} G_2 \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M \left(\sin \frac{\pi k}{M} \right)^q \right\}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

was used. The equal values of the main macroscopic characteristic of the simulated specimens, total stiffness, will give an opportunity to analyze the pure effect of the stochasticity on the main fracture parameters. The increase in the fractal dimension is linked with the growing homogeneity of the stochastic media.

An important feature of the proposed approach is the possibility of including the structural features of particular materials, such as strength anisotropy, presence of interfaces, etc. It can be practically implemented by the change of fractal tree's structure at different levels. For example, layered materials can be represented by fractal trees with branches (the level $n=1$), corresponding with different layers. Concrete cases of anisotropy can be considered by the formulation of different constitutive equations for various parts of the fractal tree and/or by the complication of conditions of the fracture transition to the upper levels of the tree. The solutions obtained for the local region, e.g. for particular level, may thereby serve as the initial point in the fracture analysis on large spatial scales. The description of more complicated cases of fracture (mixed-mode, etc.) could be implemented with the introduction of additional damage parameters, describing microdefects of different deformation modes.

The fractal model for spatiotemporal damage evolution is applicable to the cases with the absence of initial notches or macroscopic cracks. In such cases the reformulation of the proposed approach is necessary for account for the crack-damage interaction and stress redistribution near the crack tip in terms of stress-intensity factors.

3. FRACTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CRACK FRONTS

The scenario of crack propagation process is sufficiently complicated for the stochastic composites. The macroscopic defect interacts with a non-uniform evolution of microdefects at different scale levels. A stochastic distribution of mechanical properties and elements' orientations causes a stress localization and a multiple growth of fracture nucleus. The main factor governing this process is the interaction of a propagating microcrack with the accumulating damage. Some ideas for crack-damage or crack-microcrack interactions were proposed [24-27].

In the case of natural or artificial crack (initiated by a V-shape notch, for example) the load redistribution procedure together with the crack-microcrack interactions is the dominant factor in crack propagation. So, the state equations (1),(2) should be complemented with the relation accounting the exact crack in terms of the stress intensity factors. The stress redistribution in this case could be described on the basis of known results, for example by formulas from [28].

Some attempts to use the fractal approach in the problems of fracture mechanics [29] showed that the stress intensity factor depends strongly on the geometry of the real crack. But the direct account of it in the model is relatively complex.

Let us study the application of the fractal approach for propagating crack characterization by an example of the rectangular region, which contains the symmetry plane (and an apex) of the V-shape notch. We shall consider this region to be the cross-section of the rectangular beam loaded with a constant force S^* on its ends. The direction of the force is perpendicular to the region. We shall divide this cross-section into the elements with dimensions corresponding to the requirements of the elementary volume. In this section, we shall again simulate the spatial scatter of mechanical properties in terms of random stiffness.

The system of the constitutive equations consist of the load redistribution law for structural elements due to the crack propagation and to the kinetic quasi-linear equation of damage accumulation. The latter could be written in the form [30,31] (another indices in comparison with eq.(2) resulted from the type of discretization),

$$\dot{p}^{ij} = A\sigma^{ij} + Bp^{ij} , \quad (8)$$

where the pair (i,j) corresponds to the element of the i-th row and j-th column, rows are perpendicular to the crack front. $\sigma^{ij} = \sigma_z^{ij}$ is a parameter of a macroscopic stress tensor and z is the load direction. In order to fulfill automatically the equilibrium law, let us consider

$$\bar{G}^i = \sum_{j=1}^N G^{ij} = const \quad (9)$$

where G^{ij} is the stiffness of the (i,j)-element, N - the number of columns of the elements. Let us note that we distribute stiffness over all elements of the cross-section, even in the region of the initial notch.

The load redistribution law must reflect the stress field disturbance caused by a crack propagation. Because of the spatial non-uniformity of this process, linked with the random character of mechanical properties, one should take into account the difference of the crack length along its front. So, we exploit the well known relation

$$\sigma_z = \frac{K_j}{(2\pi y)^{1/2}} , \quad (10)$$

where y is a coordinate perpendicular to a crack front. One may obtain the stress redistribution relationship by integrating eq.(10) along the y axis in the rows :

$$\sigma^{ij} = K_{ij}\sigma_{in}^{ij} , \quad (11)$$

where the initial stress value (depending on the random stiffness of elements) is,

$$\sigma_{in}^{ij} = S * \frac{G^{ij}}{Gl_x l_y} . \quad (12)$$

Here l_x and l_y are the dimensions of the structural element along x and y axes, respectively.

The reloading coefficients K_{ij} reflect two interacting fracture mechanisms: the crack propagation under a constant load (in terms of K_I) and the local failure of the elements in the crack front caused by the damage evolution. The second mechanism is accounted by eq.(8): the increase caused by the stress redistribution accelerates the evolution of microcrack ensemble. The coefficients K_{ij} can be obtained from the formula

$$K_{ij} = \bar{K}_{ij} \frac{\bar{G}^i}{\bar{G}^i} , \quad (13)$$

where \bar{K}_{ij} are linked with the stress intensity factor of the i-th row of the crack front:

$$\bar{K}_{ij} = K_I^i \sqrt{\pi l_y} (\sqrt{j+1-l_i} - \sqrt{j-l_i}) , \quad (14)$$

with l_i being the number of columns in the i-th row occupied by the crack. The second multiplier in eq.(13) accounts for the decrease of the total stiffness for the i-th row under the crack

propagation and failure of structural elements: $\tilde{G}^i = \sum_{j=l_i}^N (G^{ij} \bar{K}^{ij})$ (we shall assume that for the failed element its stiffness becomes zero). The value of K_i^i could be approximated by the known relations, for example, by [29]:

$$K_i^i = S * \bar{G}^i \frac{1.11 - 5(l_i / N)^4}{\bar{G}^i (1 - l_i / N)} \quad (15)$$

or by any other approximation for K_i^i which could be obtained from the modern handbooks of stress intensity factors.

The numerical simulation was fulfilled for the case of $N = 100$ (i.e. the square lattice of 10000 elements). Such dimensions of a grid allow to analyze the fractal properties of the fracture process: they meet the traditional requirements of the fractal theory that the size ratio for a cluster and its element should be not less than 10. The V-shape notch occupies 15 per cent of specimen's width.

The numerical simulation had shown that the process of the macrocrack propagation is more uniform for more homogeneous materials: the crack front in this case is less indented. It could be naturally explained: in the limit of $K_{0.5} = 1/2$ one has the totally deterministic situation with $G^{ij} = 2G_q$ and the crack, moving as a straight line. This case is the traditional one for the linear fracture mechanics where the crack front length is considered to be a constant value along the direction parallel to the notch apex. The fractal dimension of the crack front was calculated for each time step. It was shown [30,31] that the fractal dimension for each case of stochasticity insufficiently changes with the crack propagation though the crack front's shape varies largely. Calculations, carried out for various statistical realizations (various random distributions of material's properties over the region) for three cases of stochasticity give the value of the fractal (Hausdorff-Besikovitch) dimension for a propagating cracks

$$\begin{aligned} D_{HB} &= 0.59 \pm 0.02 \quad \text{for} \quad K_{0.5} = 0.1683 \quad , \\ D_{HB} &= 0.68 \pm 0.03 \quad \text{for} \quad K_{0.5} = 0.25 \quad , \\ D_{HB} &= 0.78 \pm 0.04 \quad \text{for} \quad K_{0.5} = 0.4997 \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Thus, the fractal dimension of the crack's front in stochastic materials is an invariant characteristic of its propagation and consequently of the fracture process. Evidently, the distribution character of mechanical properties, the notch geometry will define the basic parameters of the fractal cluster (its dimension) and hence the topological aspects of the crack propagation. Nowadays, the experimental definition of the fractal characteristics for the fracture process becomes to some extent a traditional technique. By comparing the invariant fracture parameter - the fractal dimension obtained from the experimental data treatment (D_{HB}^e) and from numerical simulation (D_{HB}^{ns}) and minimizing the norm $\|D_{HB}^e - D_{HB}^{ns}\|$ (which is a measure of adequacy of the model) one can change the model parameters (the local fracture criterion, the approximation for stress intensity factor, etc.) in order to receive more adequate and correct description.

4. CONCLUSION

The main result of the investigation of fracture process in stochastic materials is the self-similar (fractal) character of its development under various conditions. It allows to propose new fracture criteria and to work out computational procedures linked with any type of the space discretization. Another advantage is the possibility of adequate account for additional information in model. This information could be obtained from the experimental data treatment or from the numerical simulation of the partial problems. The refined procedure could be used for cases of arbitrary geometry and loading law (including an account of load fluctuations).

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to the A.v.Humboldt-Stiftung for the possibilities to carry out the research project in Germany and to the host institute - Institut für Strukturmechanik DLR (Braunschweig).

References

1. Sornette, D., *Critical Transport and Failure in Continuum Crack Percolation*, J. Phys. France, Vol.49, No.8, pp.1365-1377,1988.
2. Anderson, T.L., *Application of Fractal Geometry to Damage Development and Brittle Fracture in Materials*, Scr.Met., Vol.23, No. 1, pp.97-102, 1989.
3. Matsushita, M., *Fractal Viewpoint of Fracture and Accretion*, J.Phys.Soc.Japan., Vol.54, No. 3, pp.857-860, 1985.
4. Williford, R.F., *Fractals and Multifractals in Fracture*, Scr. Met., Vol.22, pp.1749-1754, 1988.
5. Louis, E., Guinea, F., *The Fractal Nature of Fracture*, Europhys. Lett., Vol.3, pp.871-877, 1987.
6. Alava, M.J., Ritala, R.K., *Fracture of Random Fibre Networks with Non-central Forces*, J. Phys. Condens. Matter., Vol.2, No. 28, pp.6093-6107, 1990.
7. Wu, X., Zhu, Z., Ke, W. *The Theoretical Basis of Application of Fractal to Fracture Physics*, J. Appl. Phys., Vol.67, No. 2, pp.1126-1127, 1990.
8. Heping, X., *The Fractal Effect of Irregularity of Crack Branching on the Fracture Toughness of Brittle Materials*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol.41, No. 4, pp.267-274, 1989.
9. Mandelbrot, B.B. *Fractals, Form, Chance and Dimension*, Freeman, San-Fransisco 1977, pp.365.
10. Mandelbrot, B.B. *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*. Freeman, San-Fransisco 1982, pp.232.
11. Takayasu, H., *Fractals in the Physical Sciences*, Manchester University Press, Manchester/ New York 1989, pp.170.
12. Peitigen, H.O., Jürgens, H., Saupe, D., *Chaos and Fractals. New Frontiers of Science*, Springer-Verlag, New York e.a. 1992, pp.984.
13. Mandelbrot, B.B., Passoja, D.E., Paullay, A.J. *The fractal character of fracture surfaces of metals*, Nature, Vol.308, pp.721-722, 1984.
14. Lung, C.W., Zhang, S.Z., *Fractal Dimension of Fractured Surface in Materials*, Int. Cent. Theor. Phys., Trieste 1989, pp. 11.
15. Dauskardt, R.H., Haubensak, F., Ritchie, R.O. *On the Interpretation of the Fractal Character of Fracture Surfaces*, Acta metall. mater., Vol.38, No. 2, pp.143-159, 1990.
16. Hermann, H.J., Hansen A., *Fracture of Disordered Elastic Lattices in Two Dimensions*, Phys. Rev. B., Vol.39, No. 1, pp.637-648, 1989.
17. Hinrichsen, E.L., Hansen, A., Roux, S., *A Fracture Growth Model*, Europhys. Lett., Vol.8, No. 1, pp.1-7, 1989.
18. Lemaitre, J., Chaboche, J.-L., *Mechanics of Solid Materials*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 1990, pp.556.
19. Krajcinovic, D., Fonseka, G.V., *The Continuous Damage Theory of Brittle Materials*, Trans. ASME. J.Appl.Mech., Vol.48, No. 4, 809-824, 1981.

20. Chaboche, J.L., *Continuum Damage Mechanics*, Trans. ASME. J.Appl.Mech., Vol.55, No. 1, pp.59-72, 1988.
21. Silberschmidt, V. V., *Fractal Models in Fracture Analysis*, Ural Academic Press, Sverdlovsk 1990, pp.48 (in Russian).
22. Silberschmidt, V.V., Silberschmidt, V.G., *Fractal Models in Rock Fracture Analysis*, Terra Nova, Vol.2, No. 5, pp.483-487, 1990.
23. V.V.Silberschmidt, *Mathematical Modelling and Fractal Analysis of Stochastic Fracture Process*, In Mathematical Modelling and Applied Mathematics. Proc. IMACS Conf. Eds. A.Samarsky, M.Sapagovas, Elsevier Science Publishers B.V. (North Holland) 1992, pp.399-406.
24. Kachanov, M., Laures, J.-P., *Three-dimensional Problems of Strongly Interacting Arbitrary Located Penny-shaped Cracks*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol.41, No. 4, pp.289-313, 1989.
25. Botsis, J., *Crack and Damage Propagation in Polystyrene under Fatigue Loading*, Polymer, Vol.29, p.457-469, 1988.
26. Lua, Y.J., Liu, K.L., Belytchko, T, *A Stochastic Damage Model for the Rupture Prediction of a Multi-phase Solid*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol.55, pp.321-361, 1992.
27. Gorelik, M., Chudnovsky, A. *On the Strong Crack-Microcrack Interaction Problem*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol.56, pp.R9-R14, 1992.
28. Cherepanov, G.P, *Mechanics of Brittle Fracture*. New York: McGraw-Hill 1979, pp.930.
29. Heping, X., *The fractal effect of irregularity of crack branching on the fracture toughness of brittle materials*, Int.J.Fracture, Vol.41, pp.267-274, 1989.
30. Silberschmidt, V. V. *Fractal Analysis of Crack Propagation*, Ural Academic Press, Sverdlovsk 1991, pp.48 (in Russian).
31. Silberschmidt, V.V., *The Fractal Characterization of Propagating Cracks*, Int. J. Fracture, Vol.56, R33-R38, 1992.